

FEATURES OF A TIMELY APPROACH TO ANEMIA IN CHILDREN

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Annotation

Anemia is an insidious disease. Internal problems and serious illnesses do not always cause the development of deficiency. The environment, poor nutrition, bad habits - all this affects the composition of the blood. Don't self-medicate! If you consult a doctor in a timely manner, you can avoid serious consequences for the body.

Separately, I would like to remind women that without a sufficient amount of iron in the blood there will be no luxurious shiny hair, long nails and healthy skin. Choose trusted clinics with a modern approach to identifying the causes, symptoms and treatment of anemia.

Key words: Anemia hemoglobin, ferritin.

Relevance of the problem. There are a number of factors that contribute to the development of anemia in children. Antenatal factors act throughout the entire period of fetal development. For normal hematopoiesis during pregnancy, the fetal body must receive and accumulate enough iron (the average amount is 300 mg).

The most active transfer of iron from the mother and its accumulation in the child's body occurs at 28–32 weeks. If pregnancy is not progressing properly during this period, iron metabolism is disrupted and its reserves are insufficiently accumulated in the fetus. Anemia in children often occurs if a woman suffered

from iron deficiency during pregnancy. Intrapartum factors are in most cases associated with extensive blood loss during childbirth. This happens when placental abruption, untimely ligation of the umbilical cord, or the use of obstetric aids that can injure the woman in labor. Premature birth also contributes to the development of anemia in children, starting from the third month of life. Postnatal factors contribute to the development of iron deficiency anemia immediately after birth. They can be exogenous and endogenous. Endogenous anemia is provoked by certain conditions: hemolytic disease o Anemia in children can be due to a number of other reasons: regular blood loss, for example, due to diseases of the hematopoietic organs; vitamin deficiency; nutritional reasons, when there is not enough iron in mother's milk; impaired absorption and metabolism of iron.

In addition, insufficient hemoglobin is affected by rare walks in the fresh air, poisoning, exposure to radiation, physical inactivity, infections and accelerated growth of the child. The development of anemia in children is due to active growth, an intensive process of erythropoiesis, an increase in the number of formed elements and the volume of circulating blood. However, the hematopoietic apparatus in children is still immature and very vulnerable to various negative influences. A healthy hematopoietic system requires a certain supply of iron, protein, vitamins and other useful components, so the slightest error in nutrition, infections of various kinds, and toxic effects on the body can cause the development of anemia in a baby. Children after six months, whose neonatal reserves of useful components are gradually coming to an end, are especially sensitive to iron deficiency. Long-term anemia in children without proper treatment is accompanied by hypoxia, changes in organs and tissues. A child with anemia lags behind his peers in physical and mental development, more often suffers from infections, and is prone to the development of pathological processes and complications after illnesses.

Diagnostic measures are based on laboratory blood tests. Clinical analysis

accurately shows a decrease in hemoglobin levels. A biochemical blood test will determine the level of serum iron, the degree of saturation of transferrin with iron, its concentration in the serum, as well as the amount of bilirubin and vitamins. In complex cases of anemia in a child, specialists perform a bone marrow puncture for further research. During the diagnostic process, doctors identify the severity of the pathology, taking into account the content of red blood cells and hemoglobin. Some children need additional examination. The attending physician may prescribe an ultrasound examination of the abdominal cavity and kidneys, as well as esophagogastroduodenoscopy. Consultations with narrow specialists are indicated - gastroenterologist, gynecologist, nephrologist. Based on the examination results, clinical recommendations for the treatment of anemia are given.

Factors contributing to the development of anemia in children are divided into antenatal, intranatal and postnatal.

Antenatal factors act during intrauterine development. For the normal course of hematopoiesis in a child during pregnancy, his body must receive from the mother and accumulate a sufficient amount of iron (about 300 mg). The most intense transfer of iron from the pregnant woman and its deposition in the fetus occurs at 28-32 weeks of gestation. Disruption of the normal course of pregnancy during this period (gestosis, fetoplacental insufficiency, threat of miscarriage, premature placental abruption, bleeding, infectious diseases of the mother, exacerbation of chronic processes) leads to disruption of iron metabolism and its insufficient accumulation in the child's body. Anemia in children occurs if the woman also suffered from anemia during pregnancy.

Multiple pregnancy contributes to the development of anemia in newborns.

Intrapartum factors of anemia in children are associated mainly with blood loss during childbirth. Blood loss is possible in the event of premature placental abruption during childbirth, early or late ligation of the umbilical cord, bleeding

from the umbilical cord when it is not properly processed, or the use of traumatic obstetric aids. Premature birth leads to the fact that anemia is detected in all premature babies from birth or from approximately the 3rd month of life.

Postnatal factors of anemia in children turn on after birth and can be endogenous or exogenous. The causes of endogenous anemia in children can be damage to red blood cells due to hemolytic disease of the newborn, abnormal hemoglobin synthesis, and primary constitutional failure of the bone marrow.

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